

A Study on the Lead dioxide Decomposed Product of So-called Etheneal Blue Peroxychromic Acid

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Ethereal blue peroxychromic acid decomposes in lead dioxide to chromate. Oxidising powers of the different decomposition products under different conditions have been determined and it has been found that the results are in agreement with the formula, $\text{Cr}_2(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_{10})_3$ proposed by Rai¹⁻⁵ rather than with CrO_3 suggested by Schwarz and Giese⁶.

Experimental

ALL the reagents employed were of A.R. quality. Purification of ether was carried out by shaking it with concentrated solution of ferrous sulphate and then distilling. Before mixing all the solutions were well cooled in a refrigerator. The blue compound was prepared by adding varying volumes of hydrogen peroxide (20 vol.) to a mixture of 5% (W/V) potassium dichromate (10 ml.), 2*N*-sulphuric acid (10 ml.) and ether (120 ml.). The ethereal blue solution thus formed was separated, washed for four or five times with ice-cold distilled water. This was separated finally, kept in the refrigerator for 2 or 3 hr in order to freeze out water, then decanted off into a previously dried and cooled flask and kept in ice to proceed the following studies :

Preparation of various decomposition products in presence or absence of lead dioxide : 5 ml. of each sample of the blue compound was allowed to decompose

- (i) in each of four Erlenmeyer flasks each containing 20 ml. of distilled water,
- (ii) in each of four dried Erlenmeyer flasks under open conditions,
- (iii) in each of four well dried Erlenmeyer flasks each containing 0.3 gm. of pure and dried lead dioxide under open conditions.

Each decomposition was complete in about 12 hr. In absence of lead dioxide, a yellow coloured solution was obtained in (i) type decomposition while brown residue was formed in the decomposition of type (ii). In presence of lead dioxide, the resulting product seemed to be dark brown coloured.

Oxidising power of the blue compound :

5 ml. of each of the samples of the blue compound was added to aqueous solution of potassium iodide

and 10 ml. of 2*N*-sulphuric acid, the liberated iodine was titrated against standard sodium thiosulphate solution (*N*/42) using starch as an indicator to a green end point. The titre values so obtained gave the total oxidising power of the blue compound as such.

Oxidising power of the various decomposition products :

Oxidising powers of water, open and lead dioxide decomposed products were determined as follows :

Unoxidised decomposition products : To each of the contents of the flasks from water and open decomposition products from each sample was added 5 ml. of 10% potassium iodide and acidified with 10 ml. of 2*N*-sulphuric acid. The liberated iodine was titrated against the same sodium thiosulphate solution using starch as an indicator.

The oxidising power of lead dioxide decomposed product obtained from each sample was carried out by treating it with 10 ml. of 2*N*-sulphuric acid and filtering in a flask containing aqueous solution of potassium iodide and the liberated iodine was titrated iodometrically as usual.

Oxidised decomposition products : The contents of the flasks of water and open types of decomposition products were oxidised by adding 20 ml. of *N*-sodium hydroxide followed by 5 ml. 30% (100 vol.) hydrogen peroxide. The excess of peroxide was decomposed by prolonged boiling till the frothing had ceased. The contents were then cooled to room temperature, acidified with 2*N*-sulphuric acid and titrated against the same sodium thiosulphate solution after adding potassium iodide and starch solution.

The contents of the flasks of lead dioxide decomposed product were treated with 10 ml. of 2*N*-sulphuric acid and filtered in a clean Erlenmeyer flask. The filtrate along with washings was oxidised and titrated iodometrically with the similar procedure as described above.

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Discussion

The earlier workers⁷⁻⁹ supporting the formula, CrO_5 for the blue compound did not consider the

reduction of $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ ions to Cr^{3+} ions by hydrogen peroxide in presence of hydrogen ions during the formation of blue peroxychromic acid. Rai¹⁰ also prepared the blue compound by using potassium dichromate, hydrogen peroxide and chromium sulphate solutions without the presence of any acid. This mode of the reaction in the formation of blue peroxychromic acid suggests the presence of trivalent chromium in its composition and therefore on decomposition it furnishes trivalent chromium compounds, while some workers^{11,12} centered their studies on intermediates formed during the decomposition suggesting the presence of Cr(III) ion in them and did not take notice of the existence of Cr(III) originally present in the blue compound.

If it is accepted that the study of the blue compound is a study of partly decomposed species from it as the decomposition might have occurred during the washings with water and subsequent storage before analysis. These steps were carried out during the formation of the blue peroxychromic acid so as to remove excess of hydrogen peroxide and water from the ethereal solution. With this view various ratios of oxidising power of the blue compound and its decomposition products under study were found to be similar within experimental errors to those of the oxidising power of unwashed and freshly prepared blue peroxychromic acid (obtained using small amount of hydrogen peroxide) and its decomposition products except open decomposition which was found to be affected by traces of water suggesting thereby the study of the authentic blue compound and its decomposition products and not the decomposed species.

Observations recorded in the Table 1 show that :

(i) When ethereal blue compound is decomposed in each of water and open bottle, the titre values shown in columns (c, e) are different for the decomposition products showing that different compounds are formed under these different conditions.

(ii) The titre values of the different decomposition products increase when oxidised with 30% hydrogen peroxide in strongly alkaline medium and attain the same value for each product (columns d, f). This

suggests the presence of both trivalent and hexavalent chromium in the decomposed products.

(iii) When the blue compound is decomposed in presence of lead dioxide, the titre value of the resulting product is almost identical to that obtained after oxidation in absence of lead dioxide. This evidently shows that trivalent chromium present in the blue compound gets oxidised during the decomposition in presence of lead dioxide into hexavalent chromium.

The total oxidising power of the blue compound in terms of the available oxygen atoms may be expressed as :—

Rai and co-workers (*loc. cit.*) have suggested that the water decomposition of ethereal blue compound is chromium dichromate, $\text{Cr}_2(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7)_3$. The blue compound would decompose in water as :—

The oxidising power of water decomposition product will be similar to that of other dichromates, thus

Blue compound when decomposed in open bottle, gives $\text{Cr}_2(\text{CrO}_4)_3$ as suggested by Rajput and Rai (*loc. cit.*)

when titrated iodometrically, it gives

TABLE 1

		5% $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$: 10 ml.		2N- H_2SO_4 : 10 ml. Sodium thiosulphate solution : N/42.		Ether : 120 ml.		20 Vol. H_2O_2 : Varying volume,				
Vol. of H_2O_2	Blue compd.	Sod. thiosulphate used in titrating						R A T I O S				
		Decomposition in						b/c	d/c	f/e	b/e	b/g
		Water		Open		PbO ₂						
		Unoxid.	Oxid.	Unoxid.	Oxid.	Unoxid.	Oxid.					
a	b	c	d	e	f	g	h					
5	10.60	5.30	6.50	4.00	6.45	6.30	6.40	2.00	1.23	1.61	2.65	1.68
10	11.95	6.10	7.90	4.55	7.80	7.80	7.85	1.96	1.29	1.71	2.63	1.53
15	10.05	5.15	6.25	3.80	6.20	6.10	6.20	1.95	1.21	1.63	2.64	1.62
20	9.10	4.60	5.70	3.40	5.75	5.80	5.70	1.98	1.24	1.69	2.67	1.57

TABLE 2

Formula	R A T I O S									
	b/c		d/c		f/e		b/e		b/g	
	calc.	found	calc.	found	calc.	found	calc.	found	calc.	found
CrO ₅	3.11	1.95	1.33	1.21	1.66	1.61	3.88	2.63	2.33	1.53
		to 2.00		to 1.29		to 1.71		to 2.67		to 1.68
Cr ₂ (Cr ₂ O ₁₀) ₃	2.00	1.95	1.33	1.21	1.66	1.61	2.50	2.63	1.50	1.53
		to 2.00		to 1.29		to 1.71		to 2.67		to 1.68

On oxidation of the water and open bottle decomposition products with hydrogen peroxide in alkaline solution alkali chromates are formed :

In presence of acid each gm. atom of Cr(VI) would give 1.5 gm. atom of available oxygen as usual.

When the blue compound is decomposed in presence of lead dioxide, the decomposition would occur as :

or

The resulting product on treatment with dilute sulphuric acid releases chromic acid which liberates iodine from iodide as usual.

The observations recorded in table 2 show that the experimental results are in close agreement with the

theoretical ones based on Rai's formula, Cr₂(Cr₂O₁₀)₃ for the blue peroxychromic acid which is chromium peroxychromate containing both trivalent and hexavalent chromium.

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